

Supp fig1

Supp fig2

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Supp fig3

A

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Supp fig5

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Supplemental figure legends:

Supp Fig.1: *Short-term Postnatal hypothyroidism does not impact the expression of metabolic genes in Gastrocnemius in adult male mice fed either Chow or HFD.*

To assess the long-term impact of short-term postnatal hypothyroidism on metabolism in adult male mice fed either CHOW or HFD, the expression of genes involved in different metabolic pathways was measured in the gastrocnemius by relative RT-qPCR. Different metabolic pathways have been tested: uncoupling (*ucp2* and *ucp3*), calcium futile cycle (*sarcolipin*, *serca2a*, *serca2b* and *ryr1*), glucose metabolism (*glycogen synthase* and *pgca1*) CTRL are in black (CHOW n=6, HFD=5) and Post-HT in purple (CHOW n=5, HFD=6). Each dot represents an animal the mean per condition was calculated and indicated by a black line, error bars are +/- SEM. The reference group was CTRL CHOW for each gene. a one-way ANOVA on each gene was run followed by a post-hoc Dunnett's multiple comparisons test to compare sub groups, ie CTRL versus Post-HT on CHOW or CTRL versus Post-HT on HFD. No statistical difference was observed.

Supp Fig.2: *Short-term Prenatal hypothyroidism does not impact body weight and glycemia in the adult.*

Different parameters were analyzed to assess the consequence of short-term prenatal hypothyroidism on the physiology of CHOW fed adult male mice either CTRL (n=13, in black) or Pre-HT (n=7, in green). A- Body weight was followed from PND20 to PND200. Each dot represents the mean for the different individuals of a group, the error bars +/- SEM. Daily food intake (B) as well as fed (C) and fasted (D) glycemia were measured around 3 months of age (PND85 to PND95). A GTT (E) was performed at PND95 and an ITT (F) at PND110. Each dot represents the mean for the different individuals of a group, the error bars +/- SEM. At the end of the experiment (PND200), mice were weighted (G), tibia and femur length (H) were measured and different tissues sampled and weighted: inguinal (I) and gonadal (J) WAT and BAT (K). For C, D, G, H, I, each dot represents an animal, the mean is indicated and error bars stand for +/- SEM. To evaluate the statistical difference between the CTRL and the Pre-HT groups, an unpaired t-test with Welch's correction was used. No significant difference was detected.

Supp Fig.3: *Short-term Prenatal hypothyroidism barely impacts the expression of metabolic genes in liver and BAT.*

To assess the long-term impact of short-term prenatal hypothyroidism on metabolism in adult male mice (PND200), the expression of genes involved in different metabolic pathways was measured in liver (A) and BAT (B) two key metabolic organs by relative RT-qPCR. A-In liver different pathways were analyzed: FA synthesis (*Fas*, *Acc*, *Me*, *Chrebp* and *Scd-1*), FA β -oxidation (*Cpt1a*, *Cpt1b* and *Pgc1b*) and glucose metabolism (*Pepck*, *Gk* and *L-Pk*). B- In BAT, FA synthesis (*Fas*, *Acc*, and *Chrebp*) and FA β -oxidation (*Cpt1a*, *Cpt1b* and *Pgc1b*) as well as markers of BAT activity (*Ucp1*, *Phospho1*, *Ckb* and *Pgc1a*) were measured. CTRL are in black (n=13) and Pre-HT in green (n=7). Each dot represents an animal, the mean is indicated and error bars stand for +/- SEM. To evaluate the statistical difference between the CTRL and the Pre-HT groups, an unpaired t-test with Welch's correction was used. No significant difference was observed.

Supp Fig.4: *Short-term postnatal hypothyroidism hardly modifies the expression of metabolic genes under HFD.*

3.5 month-old CTRL (n=7 in black) and Post-HT (n=8 in purple) male mice were switched from Chow to a High Fat Diet (HFD). Tissues were sampled after 80 days (PND210). The expression of genes involved in different metabolic pathways was measured in liver (A) and BAT (B) two key metabolic organs by relative RT-qPCR. CTRL (n=13) and Post-HT (n=6) CHOW mice were the same one as those presented in Figure 6 and were the same age as HFD fed animals at the time of tissue sampling. Stars indicated significant difference between CTRL and Post-HT on a given diet. The number indicated on top of the HFD bars represent for each group the induction factor between the HFD versus CHOW conditions (PND200). (A) In liver different pathways were analyzed: FA synthesis (*Fas*, *Acc*, *Me*, *Chrebp* and *Scd-1*), FA β -oxidation (*Cpt1a*, *Cpt1b* and *Pgc1b*) and glucose metabolism (*Pepck*, *Gk* and *L-Pk*). (I) In BAT, FA synthesis (*Fas*, *Acc*, and *Chrebp*) and FA β -oxidation (*Cpt1a*, *Cpt1b* and *Pgc1b*) as well as markers of BAT activity (*Ucp1*, *Phospho1*, *Ckb* and *Pgc1a*) were measured. Each dot represents an animal, the mean is indicated and error bars stand for +/- SEM. The number indicated on top of the HFD bars represent for each group the induction factor between the Chow versus HFD conditions. A one-way ANOVA was run for each gene followed by a post-hoc Dunnett's multiple comparisons test to compare CTRL versus Post-HT under HFD. *stands for $0,005 \leq p \leq 0,05$, ** for $0,001 \leq p \leq 0,005$.

Supp Figure 5: *Short-term Prenatal hypothyroidism does not predispose to diet induced obesity*

3.5 month-old CTRL (n=7 in black) and Pre-HT (n=10 in green) male mice were switched from CHOW to High Fat Diet (HFD). We measured their body weight gain after the switch during all the period on HFD (A) and also expressed it as the percentage of their initial weight (B). Food intake (C) was calculated over the first 2 weeks on HFD. Measurement of fasted glycemia (D) and GTT (E) were performed after 10 weeks of HFD and ITT (F) after 13 weeks. To assess the long-term impact of short-term prenatal hypothyroidism on the response to diet induced obesity the expression of genes involved in different metabolic pathways was measured by relative RT-qPCR in liver (G) and BAT (H) two key metabolic organs. (G) In liver different pathways were analyzed: FA synthesis (*Fas*, *Acc*, *Me*, *Chrebp* and *Scd-1*), FA β -oxidation (*Cpt1a*, *Cpt1b* and *Pgc1b*) and glucose metabolism (*Pepck*, *Gk* and *L-Pk*). (H) In BAT, FA synthesis (*Fas*, *Acc*, and *Chrebp*) and FA β -oxidation (*Cpt1a*, *Cpt1b* and *Pgc1b*) as well as markers of BAT activity (*Ucp1*, *Phospho1*, *Ckb* and *Pgc1a*) were measured. Stars indicated a significant difference between CTRL and Pre-HT. Protocol ended at PND210. For A, B, E, F each dot on the curve represents the mean for the different individuals of a group, the error bars +/- SEM. As the curves for the CTRL and Pre-HT group are superposed, no statistics were performed For D, G, H, each dot represents an animal, the mean is indicated and error bars stand for +/- SEM. To evaluate the statistical difference between the CTRL and the Pre-HT groups, an unpaired t-test with Welch's correction was used. No statistical significance was observed